

Project number: 016.Veni.175.081
Title: The Sharing Economy: Societal Implications of Online Streaming
Applicant: dr. H. Datta

I would like to express my gratitude to the reviewers for evaluating my proposal and for providing valuable comments. Below, I outline my responses to each of their concerns.

Response to Reviewer 1 (Evaluation: A)

I thank Reviewer 1 for complimenting me on my past performance and my pipeline. Further, I thank him/her for recognizing the novelty, relevance, and potential for public attention of my proposal.

(1): Reviewer 1 states that the proposed “*dissemination strategy seems a bit ambitious*”. I agree that using social media may be more efficient than engaging in traditional offline activities. **I already actively use social media** (e.g., blog posts on *emerge.nl*, *totheater.nl*). The proposed offline strategy is feasible, given that **I regularly speak at industry conferences** (e.g., Eurosonic Noorderslag, 01/2015 and 01/2016), **give research-based workshops** (Spotify, 01/2016) **and talk to executives** (Buma/Stemra, 2014-now). On top of that, my department disseminates knowledge via **AiMark Summits** and **MSI Trustee Meetings**, two excellent international outlets that bring together leading academics with multiple captains of industry. I agree my strategy is ambitious, but it is also feasible.

Response to Reviewer 2 (Evaluation: UF)

(2): I thank reviewer 2 for critically evaluating my work and making valuable suggestions. He/she states that it is “hard to assess [my] rank [with] only **one publication with senior co-authors**.” I was surprised by this comment, which also stands in contrast to Reviewer 1’s evaluation. I would like to provide additional data for an accurate assessment relative to my field of quantitative marketing.

1. The **average number of top publications** for PhDs two years after graduation (23 months in my case) is according to the most recent data (taken from Rajiv et al. 2015) **.65**. According to the same data, the **top 4%-20% junior researchers** in my field **have 1.37 publications**. In comparison, I have one top publication. This publication was recently chosen by a jury consisting of senior members of the editorial board as one of only 5 finalists for the **best paper award** in the *Journal of Marketing Research* (JMR). So, yes, I “only” have one top publication, but my objective is to write high quality papers, and being a finalist for the JMR best paper speaks to this. Also, I am in my early career where developments in productivity can change quickly. Indeed, case in point is that since writing the proposal, I now have **two articles in the 2nd round** at *Marketing Science* and *the Journal of Marketing*, both top marketing journals.
2. I acknowledge there may be differences between research fields. In marketing, it is common **to work together with senior co-authors** in thesis work. These collaborations are considered a **sign of quality** and **good practice** at the start of one’s career. Note also that articles published in the top target journals **have 2.81 authors on average**, see table below.

Number of authors	1	2	3	4	5+	
Number of articles	23 (7%)	97 (30%)	144 (45%)	38 (12%)	18 (6%)	Mean = 2.81

Sample: All articles in *Journal of Marketing*, *Journal of Marketing Research*, and *Marketing Science* (2014-2016).

(3): In what follows, I answer each of the comments listed in Reviewer’s 2 report under “Final Assessment”, question b. Remaining points are discussed subsequently.

1. *Comment: “It is important to model the role of intermediaries such as music labels.”. Response:* This is an excellent suggestion. Given that I have access to data on music labels, I can readily model the role of intermediaries, which will be especially relevant in the context of project 3.

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2. *Comment: In digital markets, intertemporal price discrimination is crucial to consider.*

Response: This is a very good point, and I thank reviewer 2 for this suggestion. In fact, project 3 allows me to directly address intertemporal price discrimination as I observe content availability across a wide set of vendors (e.g., first releasing content on iTunes, then on Spotify). For projects 1 and 2, the importance of intertemporal price discrimination is peripheral: in my observation period (05/2014-04/2015), sequential releases were a rare exception.

3. *Comment: Please explain the contributions and cite [all] recent relevant literature.*

Response: Lacking from the literature is an account of how (a) **demand and variety change** when consumers adopt streaming (project 1), (b) how **consumer welfare is affected** when streaming creates “lock in” effects (project 2), and (c) how streaming alters the **supply of new music**. Given **space limitations**, I opted to focus on the **key empirical articles** in the proposal. In the write-up of the paper, also analytical papers such as Thomes 2013 will receive due attention.

4. *Please address the impact of complementary markets such as live concerts and merchandizing.*

Response: Thanks for this excellent comment. Indeed, my dataset from Buma/Stemra allows me to incorporate parts of these effects (e.g., I have data on live concerts for the last 11 years).

5. *“The author needs to be more specific about the econometric model and methodology, and should provide evidence that he will be able to carry out the estimation phase in a reasonable timeframe”.*

[Further], “[t]he author has little experience on the study of digital markets”. Response: **I have estimated models with dynamic simultaneous equations** in my *Journal of Marketing Research* paper, using **data from digital markets** (Datta et al. 2015). Further, I have estimated these types of models in my **second-round papers**, and in a **collaboration with leading experts** in the field of dynamic simultaneous models (e.g., Marnik Dekimpe and Bart Bronnenberg at Tilburg, and Jan-Benedict Steenkamp at UNC Chapel Hill). Finally, I have 70,000 core hours of experience in High Performance Computing (see proposal, 4i), which ensures I can estimate models reasonably fast.

6. *Budgetary questions about items 3c and 3d (salary split between home institution and grant)*

Response: The form has been filled out according to the Veni 2016 Explanatory Notes, page 7. Last, please allow me to comment on reviewer 2’s criticism that I should “[make clear that I am] not addressing the issues of Uber/Airbnb/etc, which are more what people have in mind when they talk about the sharing economy”. Response: In my proposal, I state that I focus on online streaming as “**one out of arguably many facets of the sharing economy**” (see proposal, section 2a1). Clearly, online streaming is different from physical sharing (AirBnb/Uber). However, from a consumer perspective, **both streaming and sharing** imply favoring access over ownership of goods – which is the core idea of this proposal.

References:

- Datta, H., Foubert, B., & Van Heerde, H. J. (2015). The challenge of retaining customers acquired with free trials. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(2), 217-234.
- Rajiv, S., Chu, J., & Jiang, Z. (2015). Publication, Citation, Career Development, and Recent Trends: Empirical Evidence for Quantitative Marketing Researchers. *Customer Needs and Solutions*, 2(1), 71-90.
- Thomes, T. P. (2013). An economic analysis of online streaming music services. *Information Economics and Policy*, 25(2), 81-91.